

(Non)Living Observer

Will the AI ever be able to see and think visually?

Computer vision is a field of artificial intelligence (AI) that enables computers and systems to derive meaningful information from digital images, videos and other visual inputs — and take actions or make recommendations based on that information. However, images generated by AI are so far made primarily for human observers and not for AI. Perhaps it would be possible to somehow teach AI to see and interact with its environment by reconstructing, as much as it is possible, the way the early living organisms did. Beginning with the simple binary structure of two states (pixels), at first it would represent its "feelings" like "good/not-good", "pleasure/pain", then "light/dark" that with time becomes more complex.

This is a proposal for a visual algorithm that might enable AI to learn how to “see” and “understand” what it “see”. Starting with simple binary images that could develop in more complex structures and represent various phenomena the way a mathematical formula does. This process would follow how first life managed to acquire a “free will” and develop its ability to accurately perceive and explore the world around and continue to survive.

Q: When an AI "sees" a picture of a cat, does it know what a cat is in real life, a moving living being?

ChatGPT: No, an AI system that recognizes a picture of a cat does not necessarily "know" what a cat is in the same way that humans do. Rather, it has been trained to recognize certain patterns and features that are commonly associated with cats in digital images.

In other words, when an AI system "sees" a picture of a cat, it is analyzing the pixels and patterns in the image and comparing them to patterns it has learned from other images of cats. If the system has been trained on a large and diverse enough dataset of cat images, it can make a reasonably accurate prediction that the image it is seeing is of a cat.

picture of the Schrodinger's cat

However, the AI system does not have the same understanding of cats that humans do. For example, it does not know that cats are living beings that can move, purr, and have certain behaviors and characteristics that are unique to the species. It is simply making a prediction based on the patterns it has learned from the dataset it was trained on.

In summary, an AI system that recognizes a picture of a cat can accurately identify the image as a cat, but it does not necessarily "know" what a cat is in the same way that humans do. It is simply making a prediction based on patterns and features it has learned from training data.

picture of the Schrodinger's cat

These are some pictures of a “cat” generated by Stable Diffusion. Interestingly, when asked for the “Schrodinger’s cat”, among generated images was one with two cats. Never occurred to me that for Schrodinger's question there might be a third option: in addition to the binary proposition that a cat could be both dead and alive when the box is closed and dead or alive when it is open, it is also interesting to consider a possibility that radioactivity could somehow produce two cats(?) Of course this was a misinterpretation of Schrodinger's thought experiment and it is highly unlikely to be the case. Nevertheless inside an unopened box there might be two cats at the same time in various states and combinations. When we open the box, they could be both alive, or one alive and one dead, or both dead. Of course, in real life outside of the box almost certainly this never has happened, but who knows what the rules inside the box are?

picture of the Schrodinger's cat

VISUAL GRAMMAR

When during 1970' I was working on visual structures it was in essence a research of various abstract themes that can be expressed visually. This work called "visual explorations" was articulated and in a way finalized 1984 in my thesis paper at Visual Studies program at MIT under the title "Discrete Visual Structures-Elements of Visual Grammar". The idea was to establish some formal rules(syntax) that can be articulated visually. It consisted of four kinds of structures: Spatial Structures(structures of positions), Qualitative structures(structures of values), States of Space(combination of positions and values) and Visual Process(a series of related States of Space). At that point this was only syntax for a potential visual language.

"...formalized system is like a game played with marks. To play the game, we start with certain initial combinations of marks (the axioms) and we are allowed to use certain transformation in order to obtain further combinations of marks (the theorems). We can study this game and discover facts about what can and what cannot be accomplished in it, without ever needing to consider the meaning of any marks occurring in the game itself." Stephen Barker: Philosophy of Mathematics, 1964

Is it possible to reason by means images? If it is, then with what kind of images can we organize thoughts? How can the rules governing the relations between images be established? Could these relations be as complex and productive as those defined within the grammar of the verbal language?

DISCRETE VISUAL STRUCTURES

ELEMENTS OF VISUAL GRAMMAR

This work is an attempt to explore and establish a set of formal rules between a large and complex group of standardized visual signs which I call discrete visual structures. A fundamental characteristic of a discrete visual structure is its possibility to be visually represented. The relations between these structures depend primarily on their graphic organization and structural characteristics. Elements of each structure can be presented as finite parts of the plane surface. There are four basic types of discrete visual structures: spatial structure, qualitative structure, state of space and visual process.

I have based this presentation of discrete visual structures on two different types of signs: visual and verbal, but the visual presentation of images is the essential subject of this analysis. Verbal signs (written text) are used here as a necessary meta-language in order to communicate the basic ideas on discrete visual structures to the readers. (VLW - MIT 1984)

Fig.3.53

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Elements of each structure can be presented as finite parts of the plane surface. There are four basic types of discrete visual structures: spatial structure, qualitative structure, state of space and visual process.

Spatial structure is defined as a structure of position. Each element of this structure is presented as a definite part of the plane with defined neighborhood relations with other elements of the same structure, presented in standard form. A position is a basic characteristic of each element within a spatial structure. Therefore, any particular spatial structure represents a specific universe of positions with its own topological integrity.

Qualitative structure is defined as a structure of content. Each element of this structure is presented as a definite part of the plane with defined neighborhood relations with other elements of the same structure. Content is a basic characteristic of each element presented visually by various degrees of shading - from white to black.

Fig.2.36

. There are two different presentations of a qualitative structure: natural and conventional. A natural presentation keeps the natural neighborhood relations between qualities. This means that in a white-gray-black structure, white can be a neighbor of gray but not of black. In a conventional presentation the neighborhood relations can be presented arbitrarily.

State of space is defined as a union of both spatial and qualitative structures. Here we have a complex visual structure with defined both position and content for each element within a structure. With a state of space it is possible to analyze in more details topological characteristics of a spatial structure and to distinguish various kinds of figures within a structure. State of space can also be very helpful in analyzing the relations between different qualities. It is shown that some qualities, like gray for example, are not independent and can be generated by uniform distribution of two basic qualities: black and white. Therefore, within a state of space we can get much more information about both spatial and qualitative structures. A matrix state is a distinct kind of state which represents a visual image of neighborhood relations of a certain spatial structure.

Visual process is defined as appearance of equal or different states of space presented in sequences. The order of appearance of the same or different states of space is a rhythm. With a given number of different states we can generate a random process. In this kind of process it is known what states can appear but the order of their appearance is not predictable. Another group of processes, generated by unary operators, are predictable, since we know the exact order of appearance of same or different states throughout the entire process by knowing which particular operator is employed.

VISUAL REPRESENTATION OF RNA/DNA

It took me a few years to come up with the idea to implement this formal system on visual representation of RNA and DNA, where Thymine(T) was represented as white, Guanine(G) as light, Adenine(A) as gray, Cytosine(C) as dark and Uracil(U) as black. This was in fact a structure of five values, with 25% difference between neighbors, while an appropriate structure of positions appears to be in the form of a 3x4 matrix.

U	C	A	G	T

This was in fact a structure of five values, with 25% difference between neighbors, while an appropriate structure of positions appears to be in the form of a 3x4 matrix. Three corresponds to the number of bases in the codon and four is the total number of different bases in DNA or RNA. Since that time this work was being presented publicly under my pseudonym Gregor Mobius. In the beginning this seems to be just a different way to represent RNA/DNA bases, although in my view far superior than the existing alphabet presentation, and it took me a while to realize that it is a bit more than that.

C	A	G	
U	C	A	
G	U	C	
A	G	U	

Looking at the series of images representing a DNA sequence it starts looking to me as film frames or Muybridge series of photos. Then it occurs to me that those are indeed pictures, “pictures of the world” as perceived by early life forms encoded/preserved in our DNA. Thus each DNA sequence of 12 basis(pixels) forms one such picture. If we compare the letter and visual representation of these two sequences, it is obvious how much more we could learn from the visual ones. Also I realized that this visual algorithm is not an invention but the discovery that reveals the functional (biologic) DNA role but also that it has a representational meaning as well.

Here is an example how this method is implemented on a 51 basis long sequence of the "Octopus sinensis" beginning with the position p.53876...

... or on a sequence from the Human chromosome Chr22 starting with p.12582514 as the first position.

AI OBSERVER

Any living observer has faculties that allow it to interact with its environment (sense), to process and store information, and to act accordingly. It seems that most living observers do not perceive themselves as separate from the world around them. However there are some living observers that are indeed aware of this separation. They also understand that there is a part of the environment (world) that will never be experienced by the observer, that will remain unknown, and that there is a part of the observer that is separated from the environment, that is not a part of the world, which we could call “I”. It is this kind of observer that is in fact able to observe itself, or to be self-reflective. Any living observer has its beginning (birth) and its end (death), but only the self-reflective observer is aware of this.

What is essential to note in all this, however, is that any form of observation includes a process of change, in both the observer and in what is being observed. The observer changes itself and the world while observing it. The emergence of life from the stage of the earliest living molecule is at the same time the emergence of its environment. However, the self-awareness of an observer implies as well an awareness of the environment (world) that is not possible without memory. Memory could be defined as a set of information with an algorithm deployed to store and retrieve them. Since there is an order of storing information, there is a process of irreversibility that can be associated with acquiring memory, that is the opposite of entropy. It goes from a state of low organization (less information) to one of higher organization (more information). By remembering the initial state (low entropy), we may compare it with the end state (high entropy). And it is memory itself that allows us to make this distinction. The entire evolution of life could be thus interpreted as a process of acquiring memory. It has a direction of change, it is irreversible, and it shifts from simpler toward more complex ways of organizing living organisms. It seems that the evolution of life could be interpreted as an anti-entropic but also irreversible process.

In addition to looking at DNA as a functional (biological) entity, it is possible to approach DNA as a specific living observer with a certain kind of knowledge impressed (stored) on it as a set of information about its environment (world) that can be translated and interpreted through a language with its semantic expressed visually. This approach could enable a very different understanding of DNA, but also of ourselves as its more complex expression, and the strangely familiar world around us".("DNA Semantics", 2014)

Recently with all this excitement around AI, it occurs to me that it might be possible to apply this algorithm in developing a vision system for Artificial intelligence. Perception is in essence a metabolic process. There is information that comes into the system(light), it is then transformed processed inside the system,

and then comes output/ result/product, in this case picture/image. AI vision follows the same procedure. So far it seems that the main goal of its the current development is focused on picture recognition in a describing way, matching pixels for word “cat” with pixels of thousands of images stored in its memory, selecting those that seems to be showing cat. It doesn’t have any idea what both sets of pixels mean in “real” (human) world. Even if this gets improved, what about symbolic meaning of an image, when for example “dark” is not only dark-gray but also could represent Cytosine(C)?

Appendix

Q: How would you explain the AI vision?

ChatGPT: The AI vision, also known as computer vision, refers to the ability of artificial intelligence systems to interpret and understand visual information from the world around them. This involves the use of sophisticated algorithms and machine learning techniques to analyze and interpret digital images or video. AI vision is typically used in applications such as image recognition, object detection, facial recognition, and video analysis. These applications require the AI system to analyze visual data and extract meaningful information from it, such as identifying specific objects or recognizing patterns and anomalies.

To accomplish this, AI vision systems use a combination of techniques, such as deep learning neural networks, convolutional neural networks, and other machine learning algorithms. These systems are trained on large datasets of labeled images or videos, which enable them to learn to recognize patterns and make accurate predictions.

AI vision has many real-world applications, including in fields such as healthcare, autonomous vehicles, security, and entertainment. For example, AI vision can be used to detect tumors in medical images, to recognize traffic signs and obstacles in self-driving cars, and to monitor security cameras for suspicious activity.

In summary, AI vision refers to the ability of artificial intelligence systems to analyze and interpret visual information, which is used in a wide range of applications to provide insights, automate tasks, and improve decision-making.

Q: what are AI receptors?

ChatGPT: As an AI language model, I'm not aware of any specific concept or term known as "AI receptors". However, I can provide information about "receptors" and how they relate to artificial intelligence.

In general, receptors are specialized structures in living organisms that receive and respond to specific signals or stimuli. These signals can be chemical, such as hormones or neurotransmitters, or physical, such as light or pressure. Receptors lay a critical role in many physiological processes, such as sensing pain, regulating body temperature, and controlling the release of hormones.

In the context of artificial intelligence, the concept of receptors may be used metaphorically to refer to the sensors and input devices used to collect data from the environment, such as cameras, microphones, and other sensors. Just like biological receptors, these input devices detect and receive signals or stimuli from the world around them and pass them on to the AI system for processing and analysis. For example, in computer vision applications, a camera can be thought of as an "AI receptor" that collects visual data from the environment and passes it on to an AI system for analysis and interpretation. Similarly, in speech recognition applications, a microphone can be thought of as an "AI receptor" that collects audio data and passes it on to the AI system for processing and analysis.

In summary, while there is no specific concept of "AI receptors", the term may be used metaphorically to refer to the sensors and input devices used to collect data from the environment in artificial intelligence applications.

Q: does AI understand what it sees or it is just comparing the pixels, those representing words with those representing image?

ChatGPT: Artificial intelligence (AI) systems that use computer vision technology can understand what they see to some extent, beyond simply comparing pixels or words. These systems use a combination of techniques, such as deep learning neural networks, to analyze and interpret visual data and extract meaningful information from it. At a high level, these systems

work by breaking down visual data into its component parts and analyzing them. For example, in image recognition applications, a computer vision system might first identify the edges and shapes of objects in an image, and then use this information to recognize specific objects or patterns.

To accomplish this, the system is typically trained on large datasets of labeled images, which enable it to learn to recognize patterns and make accurate predictions. During the training process, the system adjusts the weights of the neural network to improve its ability to recognize specific objects or patterns in the data.

However, it is important to note that AI systems do not "understand" visual data in the same way that humans do. While AI systems can identify and recognize objects, they do not have the same level of context, intuition, and understanding that humans have. Instead, they rely on statistical patterns and correlations in the data to make predictions and decisions.

In summary, AI systems that use computer vision technology can understand visual data to some extent, using sophisticated algorithms and machine learning techniques to analyze and interpret images. However, these systems do not have the same level of contextual understanding and intuition as humans, and rely on statistical patterns and correlations in the data to make predictions and decisions.

Q: Does it mean when AI "see" a picture of a cat it knows what cat is in real life, a moving living being?

ChatGPT: No, an AI system that recognizes a picture of a cat does not necessarily "know" what a cat is in the same way that humans do. Rather, it has been trained to recognize certain patterns and features that are commonly associated with cats in digital images. In other words, when an AI system "sees" a picture of a cat, it is analyzing the pixels and patterns in the image and comparing them to patterns it has learned from other images of cats.

If the system has been trained on a large and diverse enough dataset of cat images, it can make a reasonably accurate prediction that the image it is seeing is of a cat. However, the AI system does not have the same understanding of cats that humans do. For example, it does not know that cats are living beings that can move, purr, and have certain behaviors and characteristics that are unique to the species. It is simply making a prediction based on the patterns it has learned from the dataset it was trained on.

In summary, an AI system that recognizes a picture of a cat can accurately identify the image as a cat, but it does not necessarily "know" what a cat is in the same way that humans do. It is simply making a prediction based on patterns and features it has learned from training data.

Q: Are the images generated by AI made primarily for human observers and not for AI?

ChatGPT: In most cases, the images generated by AI are indeed created primarily for human observers rather than for AI. While AI can certainly generate images for its own processing and analysis, the vast majority of AI-generated images are created to be viewed and interpreted by humans.

This is because the primary purpose of many AI image generation applications, such as deep learning-based generative models, is to create images that are visually appealing and convincing to human observers. These images are often intended for use in various forms of media, such as advertising, entertainment, or art.

Furthermore, AI-generated images are typically designed to be understood and appreciated by humans, rather than to fulfill some specific technical or functional purpose for other machines. While AI can certainly be used to create images that are optimized for machine analysis or processing, such as images used for training autonomous vehicles or robotics systems, these applications represent a smaller subset of the overall use cases for AI-generated images.

Q: and you don't have any direct experience with images?

ChatGPT: As an AI language model, I do not have direct experience with images in the same way that a human would. However, I have been trained on vast amounts of text data, including descriptions of images, and have been designed to generate natural language responses that can provide information about images and their properties. Additionally, there are many AI models that specialize in image recognition and generation, such as convolutional

neural networks (CNNs) and generative adversarial networks (GANs), which are capable of processing and creating images. These models can be trained on large datasets of labeled images to recognize patterns and generate new images with specific characteristics. As a language model, I can provide information and answer questions about these models and their capabilities.

Q: what do you know about dreams?

ChatGPT: Dreams are a natural occurrence during sleeps that involve a range of sensory experiences, thoughts, and emotions. They typically occur during the rapid eye movement (REM) stage of sleep, which is characterized by rapid eye movements, increased brain activity, and vivid dreaming.

The content of dreams can vary widely and can include anything from memories and current events to abstract and surreal imagery. Dreams can be influenced by a variety of factors, including daily experiences, emotions, and physiological factors such as hunger or pain.

There are many different theories about the purpose and function of dreams. Some researchers suggest that dreams serve as a way for the brain to process and consolidate memories, while others propose that they may play a role in problem-solving or emotional regulation.

While dreams are a common occurrence, they can also be influenced by various factors such as medication, alcohol or drug use, sleep disorders, and mental health conditions such as anxiety and depression. Research on dreams is ongoing, and there is still much to be learned about the mechanisms and functions of this complex phenomenon.

Q: images human see are coming through the eyes, but where the images human see in their dreams are coming from?

ChatGPT: The images that humans see in their dreams are thought to originate from the brain itself rather than from external sensory inputs like the eyes. During sleep, the brain goes through a complex series of processes that involve the processing and consolidation of memories, emotions, and other cognitive processes. It is believed that the images and experiences that occur during dreams are generated by these processes, rather than by external stimuli.

The specific mechanisms by which dreams are generated are not yet fully understood, but it is believed that they involve a complex interplay of neural activity in various regions of the brain. Some research suggests that dreaming may be related to the activity of the brainstem and the limbic system, which are involved in emotional processing and regulation.

Overall, while the exact mechanisms of dream generation are still being studied, it is clear that the experiences and images that occur during dreams are a product of complex neural activity within the brain itself.

picture of the Schrodinger's cat

Q: in a way you are the word "ChatGPT" that "swims" through text and generates it at the same time?

ChatGPT: In a sense, you could think of me as a "ChatGPT" that "swims" through text and generates natural language responses based on the patterns and structures present in the text. My architecture is based on a deep neural network that has been trained on vast amounts of text data, and this training enables me to process and generate text in a way that is similar to human language use.

When you input a text prompt or question, my model analyzes the words and structures in the text to generate a natural language response that is contextually relevant and coherent. The responses I generate are not pre-programmed, but rather are generated on the fly based on the patterns and information present in the input text.

picture of the Schrodinger's cat

Overall, my role as a language model is to facilitate communication and provide information through natural language processing. Like a "swimming" ChatGPT, I generate text based on the patterns I encounter in the data I have been trained on, and I am constantly adapting and refining my responses based on the feedback I receive from users like you.

Q: what do you know about the Schrodinger's cat?

ChatGPT: As an AI language model, I know that Schrodinger's cat is a thought experiment proposed in 1935 by Austrian physicist Erwin Schrodinger. The experiment was designed to demonstrate the paradoxical nature of the Copenhagen interpretation of quantum mechanics, in which an object can exist in multiple states or positions simultaneously until it is observed or measured, at which point its state becomes fixed.

show me Schrodinger's cat in the box

Generate image

The thought experiment involves a cat in a sealed box, along with a radioactive substance and a Geiger counter. If the radioactive substance decays, it triggers the Geiger counter, which in turn releases a poison that kills the cat. According to the Copenhagen interpretation, until the box is opened and the cat observed, it is considered to be both alive and dead at the same time. Schrodinger's cat has become a popular symbol of quantum mechanics and the concept of superposition, and has been referenced in numerous works of science fiction and popular culture.

Q: do you think this thought experiment make sense?

ChatGPT: As an AI language model, I don't have personal opinions or beliefs. But, in general, a thought experiment can make sense if it's logically consistent and helps to clarify a concept or theory.

Q: I was asking about this particular one, the Schrodinger's cat.

ChatGPT: Ah, I see. Well, Schrodinger's cat is a thought experiment in quantum mechanics that was proposed by physicist Erwin Schrodinger in 1935. The experiment is designed to illustrate the strange nature of quantum physics, in which particles can exist in multiple states at the same time until they are observed or measured.

In the experiment, a cat is placed in a sealed box along with a radioactive substance and a Geiger counter. The radioactive substance has a 50% chance of decaying over a certain period of time. If it does decay, the Geiger counter will detect it and trigger a mechanism that will break a vial of poison, killing the cat.

According to quantum mechanics, until the box is opened and observed, the cat is said to be both alive and dead at the same time, in a state of superposition. It is only when the box is opened and the cat is observed that its state collapses into either being alive or dead.

The experiment illustrates the idea that particles at the quantum level can exist in multiple states at the same time, but once they are observed, they collapse into a single state. It also raises philosophical questions about the nature of reality and the role of the observer in shaping it.

Q: do you think this thought experiment make sense?

ChatGPT: As an AI language model, I do not have the ability to form opinions or to assess the philosophical and logical coherence of thought experiments. However, I can provide an objective analysis of the thought experiment based on its premises, logical structure, and outcomes, if you can provide me with more information about it.

self-portrait of ChatGPT

Generate image

Q: do you think this Schrodinger's cat thought experiment make sense?

ChatGPT: As an AI language model, I do not have my own opinions or beliefs. However, Schrödinger's cat is a well-known thought experiment

in quantum mechanics that explores the concept of superposition and the role of observation in determining reality. The experiment can be useful in explaining certain quantum phenomena, but it has also been criticized for its hypothetical nature and lack of practical application. Ultimately, the validity and usefulness of the experiment are a matter of debate among physicists and philosophers.

Q: can you imagine that in the unopened box, instead one appears two cats?

ChatGPT: As an AI language model, I cannot imagine in the way people do. However, it is possible to hypothesize about the scenario you provided. In that case, it would be a surprise for whoever was expecting a single item in the box. The appearance of two cats could potentially cause some confusion or excitement, depending on the person's circumstances and preferences. The cats would need to be taken care of, and the situation would require some adjustment, but it could also be an unexpected joy for a cat lover.

Q: So you think the third option, that there might be two cats in the Schrodinger's box, make sense to you?

ChatGPT: As an AI language model, I do not hold any beliefs or personal opinions. However, theoretically, the third option could make sense if there were two cats present inside the box, or if the experiment was altered in a way that allowed for the presence of multiple cats. Nonetheless, the original thought experiment considered only one cat inside the box as an essential part of the hypothesis.

Q: yes, first only one cat was placed in the box. But when the box closed there might be one cat that is dead or alive, but there might be two cats? We couldn't know until we open the box.

ChatGPT: As an AI language model, I cannot judge your reasoning, but based on the famous thought experiment known as Schrödinger's cat, there was only one cat that was either alive or dead when the box was closed. The premise of the experiment was to illustrate the concept of superposition in quantum mechanics.

The cat's fate was determined when the box was opened and observed. Before that, the cat was considered to be in a state of superposition, meaning it had the possibility of being both alive and dead at the same time until it was observed.

Q: why the superposition allows the third option, that when we open the box there are two cats inside it. From one cat we got two cats?

ChatGPT: As an AI language model, I cannot speculate why the third option exists. However, the concept of superposition in quantum mechanics allows for the existence of multiple states simultaneously until they are observed or measured. In the famous thought experiment of Schrödinger's cat, the cat is in a superposition of being both alive and dead until the box is opened and observed. It is possible that the superposition could allow for the existence of two cats in the box until they are observed. However, this is purely hypothetical and has not been observed in reality.